

Swelling kinetics of powdered hydrolyzed fibroin

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ABSTRACT

We have published brief data on the degree of swelling of powdered hydrolyzed fibroin obtained from fibrous waste of natural silk. The results of the swelling kinetics of powdered hydrolyzed fibroin in acidic, alkaline solutions and water were determined and analyzed. Swelling kinetics in acidic and alkaline solutions and differences from swell kinetics in water were found. Based on the results obtained, conclusions were drawn on the mechanisms of swelling of hydrolyzed fibroin.

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1. Introduction

In the silk industry, mainly *Bombyx mori* silk is used. However, it is not possible to get all of the fiber during the spinning process. This is because the first and last parts of the fiber are much thinner than the fiber that makes up the middle part. In the process of spinning silk, these delicate parts become waste. Waste fibers make up 25-28% of the total cocoon fiber mass. There are opportunities to prepare sorbents with high sorption properties from waste silk fibers and materials for medicine and pharmaceuticals [1-3].

70-75% of natural silk fiber consists of fibroin protein. Silk fibroin consists of amorphous (α -structure and random chains) and crystalline (β -structure) parts. The study of the degree of swelling of silk fibroin is of great importance in the study of its sorption properties, the swelling properties in determining how long it is treated in what environmental solutions [4-6].

Silk fibroin is insoluble in water. Silk fibroin is obtained by washing natural silk fibers with a hot soda solution. Fibroin is insoluble in alcohol, ether, benzene, acetone, carbon (IV) sulfide and other organic solvents. Forms colloidal systems in calcium, strontium, barium salts and hydrogen halide acids, Schweitzer reagent and alkaline solutions, forming a neutral medium solution [7]. Silk fibroin is soluble in concentrated zinc chloride solution, calcium nitrate, calcium chloride, aqueous-alcoholic solutions of magnesium chloride, and ammonia solution of nickel (II) hydroxide [8].

Fibroin absorbs moisture in the water, resulting in a limited swelling of 30-40 %. The moisture retention of pure fibroin is 1.2 % lower than that of silk. Swelling of silk fibroin in water at 20°C has been found to increase fiber diameter by 18.7% and length by 1.3 % [9, 10]. The amorphous parts of natural silk fibroin absorb 70 %

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moisture, while the crystalline parts absorb 30 % moisture. Fibroin swelling is increased in acids and especially in alkaline solutions. Swelling of fibroins in alkalis may be irreversible. Swelling of silk fibroin in dilute solutions of sodium chloride and sodium nitrate salts is observed as in water [11].

By hydrolyzing natural silk fibroin in a 3 % hydrochloric acid solution, we obtained powdered hydrolyzed fibroin («HF») [12, 13]. We conducted studies to determine the degree of swelling of powdery «HF» under acidic conditions, alkaline conditions, and water. Swelling kinetics in these medium solutions were also studied.

2. Experiment

2.1 Materials

Fibrous of silk (Cleaned of additives. Khorezmipagi LLC, Urgench, Uzbekistan), HCl (chemically pure) and potassium hydroxide was purchased from Chimreaktivinvest (Uzbekistan).

2.2 Instrumentation

Bidistilled water is obtained from the “GFL 2104 Double distillation water still” device (Germany), swell meter, optical microscope ("Optika_B-150 DBR").

2.3 Procedure

2.3.1. Detection of «HF» powder swelling with a swell meter

The swelling of the «HF» powder was detected on a swell meter. On the swell meter, we found that the swelling levels of «HF» powder change over time under acidic (3%, HCl), alkaline (3%, KOH) conditions and in water. The experiments were performed at a temperature of 20°C for 192 hours. The swelling was determined using the following formula (1).

$$\alpha_v = \frac{V - V_0}{V_0} * 100\% \quad (1)$$

Here V_0 -the initial volume of the polymer, V -the vol-ume of the polymer at time- t .

2.3.2. Detection of «HF» swelling by optical microscopy

The swelling of «HF» particles was determined by optical microscopy using the Optika_B-150 DBR optical microscope in acidic (3%, HCl), alkaline (3%, KOH) conditions and bidistilled water at a temperature of 20°C.

3. Results and Discussion

Volume swelling levels of powdered «HF» were studied for 192 hours using the swell meter. Measurements on the swell meter revealed that the volumetric swelling rate of powdered «HF» in water was 15%, and the volumetric swelling levels in acidic and alkaline conditions were 23 and 70%, respectively. The swelling rate of «HF» powder was observed to be constant after 96 hours in the water, after 72 hours in an aqueous solution with acidic conditions, and after 144 hours in an aqueous solution with alkaline conditions. The high degree of swelling in an alkaline environment is due to the fact that the number of crystalline particles decreases due to «HF» structural changes and the number of amorphous particles increases.

The second-order kinetic equation was used to determine the swelling kinetics of «HF» powder in water, acidic and alkaline media at 20°C.

$$\frac{t}{\alpha} = \frac{1}{\alpha_t^2 \cdot K} + \frac{1}{\alpha_t} \cdot t \quad (2)$$

Where α is the swelling degree (%), t is the time, and K is the kinetic constant of the swelling. The value of K is determined from the dependence graph of t/α and t . For this purpose, a graph of the dependence of t/α and t for the process of swelling of «HF» in acidic (3% hydrochloric acid), alkaline (3% potassium hydroxide) solutions and water was developed (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Kinetics of swelling of «HF» powder in acidic (3% hydrochloric acid), alkaline (3% potassium hydroxide) solutions and water

As a result of the analysis of the graph, the constant values of the kinetics of swelling of «HF» powder in different media were determined. It was found that the kinetic constant values decrease from neutral to alkaline (Table 1).

Table 1 Constant values of the kinetics of swelling of «HF» powder in different media.

Parameters	In the water	In an acidic solution	In an alkaline solution
K	0.0664	0.0434	0.0144
$\alpha_{v, \max}, \%$	15	23	70

To determine the swelling of the «HF» particle, it was observed using a microscope and the diameter and length of its cylindrical particle were measured. The cylindrical shape of the «HF» particle makes it easy to perform calculations. The following expressions were used to calculate the volume of cylindrical particles.

$$S = \pi \cdot r^2 \tag{3}$$

$$V = S \cdot l \tag{4}$$

It can be said that the high value of the swelling of «HF» in an alkaline medium solution is due to an increase in the number of amorphous sections as its composition changes. Thus, in an alkaline environment, the number of crystalline sections of «HF» decreases and the number of amorphous sections increases [14].

Fig. 2 a) «HF» particle image (x400), b) «HF» particle size (X1000) obtained during swelling.

Since there are no external influences on the swelling of the «HF» particle detected by the optical microscope, it can be assumed to be absolutely true relative to the swelling degrees of the «HF» powder detected using the swell meter. The following are the analytical results of the binding kinetics of an «HF» particle in different media.

If we pay attention to the graphical results expressed in the swelling kinetics, we can see that the swelling kinetics of the «HF» particle in water is linear (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Kinetics of swelling of a «HF» particle in water

It was found that the value of the kinetic constant of swelling of an «HF» particle in water is $K = 0.0087$. Fractured straight lines were formed in the graphs representing the swelling kinetics of the «HF» particle in acidic and alkaline solutions (Fig. 4). The swelling of an «HF» particle in an alkaline medium solution can be represented by two different and the swelling in an acidic medium solution by three different linear functions. A specific change in the swelling kinetics of «HF» was observed after 631 minutes in an alkaline medium solution.

Fig. 4 Kinetics of «HF» particle swelling in alkali

In an alkaline medium solution, the value of the first swell kinetic constant of «HF» up to 631 minutes was found to be 0.0043, and the value of the second swell kinetic constant after 631 minutes was found to be 0.0013.

Fig. 5 Kinetics of swelling of «HF» particles in acid solution

Table 2 Swelling kinetic constant values of «HF» particle

Medium	The times corresponding to the graph lines	The value of the kinetic constant
In the water	Up to 391 minutes	0.0087
In alkaline solution (3%, potassium hydroxide)	Up to 631 minutes	0.0043
	After 631 minutes	0.0013
In an acidic solution (3%, hydrochloric acid)	Up to 331 minutes	0.0123
	331 minutes to 541 minutes	-0.0038
	After 541 minutes	0.0059

In the swelling kinetics of the «HF» particle in an acidic solution, a specific fracture of the line was observed after 331 minutes and refraction was observed again after 541 minutes, forming a straight line in the oblique position (Fig. 5).

The expressions of the initial swelling kinetics of an «HF» particle in different medium solutions can be compared. This is because the swelling kinetics of the «HF» particle in all three different environments represent a straightline growth state (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Initial swelling kinetics of a «HF» particle in solutions of different media

The values of the kinetic constants representing the initial swelling states of the «HF» particle are given in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Constant values of the kinetics of swelling of «HF» powder in different media

Parameters	In the water	In an acidic solution	In an alkaline solution
K	0.0087	0.0123	0.0043
$\alpha_{v, \max}$, %	110	169.5	335

During the swelling of the «HF» particle, water molecules enter between the fibroin macromolecules. As a result, the fibroin macromolecules move away from each other and the forces acting between them decrease. Therefore, the «HF» particle size increases. An increase in the size of the particles leads to an increase in the volume of the entire polymer mass. The swelling of «HF» particles in alkaline and acidic aqueous solutions was observed to be particularly high. This is because, in addition to water molecules, H^+ and OH^- ions enter between the macromolecules in «HF». The incoming H^+ and OH^- ions bind to the fibroin molecule and the macromolecule is charged [15-17].

Scheme 1 Binding of H^+ and OH^- ions to the peptide bond

As a result, the orientation of fibroin molecules that bind H^+ ions in an acidic solution is observed. Hydrogen ions enter the «HF» particle in the H_3O^+ state, not in the form of ordinary ions (H^+). At the same time, water molecules also enter the particles. Therefore, a «HF» particle absorbs more particles than it does in water. However, due to the charging of the fibroin molecular parts in the «HF» particle, the orientation process intensifies and an increase in intermolecular forces is observed. During the process, the disordered α -structures of the fibroin molecules change into β -structures. As a result, it is difficult for molecules in the solution to enter the «HF» particles, and the swelling slows down sharply.

In an alkaline aqueous solution, parts of the fibroin molecules in the «HF» particle are negatively charged by binding OH^- ions. Negatively charged parts located opposite each other are observed to be pushed away from each other. As a result, the intermolecular distances increase, allowing more molecules in the solution to enter and settle in the resulting space. Therefore, «HF» particles swell well in alkaline media solutions.

4. Conclusions

It was found that the swelling kinetics of HF particles in an alkaline medium solution are 2 different, and the swelling kinetics in an acidic medium solution is 3 different linear functions. In an alkaline medium solution, the HF particles were initially observed to swell slowly and were found to accelerate after 631 minutes. In an acidic medium solution, the swelling of the HF particles was initially observed to be slow and increased sharply after 331 minutes, and slowed down after 541 minutes. It was observed that the swelling kinetics of HF particles in water were in the same linear state.

Information on the extent to which the swelling process occurs in «HF» powders helps us to understand in which medium solutions «HF» can be processed and in which conditions the sorption process can proceed well or slowly.

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